

Observations of the African crab spider *Geraesta congoensis* (Lessert, 1943) from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: The crab spider *Geraesta congoensis* (Lessert, 1943) is endemic to Africa and was described as *Stephanopis congoensis* from the Democratic Republic of Congo. It was first recorded in South Africa in 2010, and it is known from the Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal, Limpopo, and Mpumalanga, South Africa. The general morphology of the species is described based on photographs of live specimens, and notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status are provided.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), taxonomy

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Geraesta* Simon, 1889 comprises six species and is restricted to the Afrotropical Region (World Spider Catalog, 2025). The first two African species were found to be misplaced in the genus *Stephanopis* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1869, and Benjamin (2011) transferred them both to *Geraesta*. The African species of *Geraesta* were revised by Benjamin (2015), and he recognized six species, with only *G. congoensis* (Lessert, 1943) from South Africa.

Geraesta congoensis was described as *Stephanopis congoensis* from the Democratic Republic of Congo. The species was reported for the first time in South Africa in 2010 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010). Since then, specimens have been sampled from four provinces during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) surveys (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015).

The general morphology of the species is discussed based on photographs of live specimens, with notes on colour variations. Updated notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status are provided.

METHODS

Specimens collected during SANSA are deposited as voucher specimens in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division. As part of SANSA, photographs were requested for the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Geraesta congoensis (Lessert, 1943)

Stephanopis congoensis Lessert, 1943: 333 Figs 6–8

Geraesta congoensis Benjamin, 2015: 313; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2023: 239; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010: 1051; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020: 32, 31.

Description: Size female total length 5-6 mm. Carapace almost as wide as long (Fig. 1); eyes in two recurved rows on small tubercles; anterior lateral eyes largest (Figs 3 & 4). In the adult live specimens, the carapace is brown with a paler triangular median band (Fig. 4); the integument densely covered by cream curly setae gives it a mottled appearance (Figs 3 & 4). Abdomen round; abdominal tubercles distinct to absent; abdomen dorsum colour and patterns vary from pale green (Fig. 5) to green bordered by a wide yellowish band (Figs 1 & 15); to green with dark paired spots (Figs 15–16). Some specimens without green markings. In both Lessert (1943) and Benjamin (2015) no mention is made of the green colour.

Figure 1–2. *Geraesta congoensis* 1. Female. 2. Immature male both collected in November 2017 from Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal. Credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 3–9. *Geraesta congoensis*. 3. Eye pattern anterior view. 4. Carapace dorsal view. 5. Juvenile habitus dorsal view. 6–7. Male palp. 8–9. Epigyne. Credits: 3–5. Peter Webb. 6 & 9. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 7–8. After Lessert (1943).

Leg formula 1243. Legs I and II are the same colour as the carapace; legs III and IV banded femora III and IV are translucent with narrow dark bands medially (Figs 1, 14, 16); tibiae and metatarsi I and II with 4-6 and 5-6 pairs of macro-setae respectively. Epigynum: broad medium spectrum, spermathecal orifices oval pits (Figs 8 & 9). Male. Size: TL 6.5. Carapace pale brown while abdomen varies between yellow brown to green with dark spots. Leg I and II are dark brown; legs III and IV banded (Fig. 2). Abdomen dorsum variable from green with dark spots (Figs 2 & 14) to brown (Figs 12 & 18). Palp with embolus winding once around the tegulum; a single tibial apophysis present (Figs 6 & 7).

Figures 10–12. *Geraesta congoensis*. 10. Female line drawing habitus. 11. Male dorsal habitus in alcohol. 12. Male dorsal view from Hoedspruit. Credits: 10. After Lessert (1943). 11. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 12. Wynand Uys.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: This genus is endemic to Africa and is now known from Botswana, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ivory Coast, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (-33.76, 24.81); East London (-33.01, 27.9). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park: False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); Fanie’s Island (-28.1, 32.45); Giant’s Castle Nature Reserve (-29.23, 29.48); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Scottburgh (-30.28, 30.75); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umkomaas (-30.2, 30.8); Kloof, Durban (-29.78, 30.83); Westville (-29.82, 30.92); Wartburg (-29.43, 30.57). **Limpopo:** Penge (-24.38, 30.29); Tshulu Camp (Venda) (-22.578, 30.809); Hoedspruit (-24.35, 30.95). **Mpumalanga:** Bourke’s Luck (-25.09, 30.81).

Figures 13–16. *Geraesta congoensis* showing the colour variations. 13. Female from Kloof (Peter Webb). 14. Male from Hoedspruit (Wynand Uys). 15. Female abdomen (Peter Webb). 16. Male abdomen (Peter Webb).

iNaturalist records from: Cumberland Nature Reserve, Wartburg, KZN, Westville, Mbombela, Tembe, Kwangwanasie.

LIFESTYLE

Geraesta congoensis is a rare plant-dweller that is more commonly found on shrubs and herbs but occasionally also sampled from tree canopies. With their green colour they are well camouflaged and blend in with the vegetation. It has been sampled from the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Thicket, and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION STATUS

During SANSA surveys, the species have been sampled from the following reserves: Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023); Giant's Castle Nature Reserve; Hluhluwe Nature Reserve; Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006) and Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2010). The species has a wide distribution and listed as of Least Concern. No conservation actions are recommended.

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Figures 17–19. *Geraesta congoensis*. 17. Male from Hoedspruit with green abdomen. 18. Male from Hoedspruit with brown abdomen. 19. Female from Hoedspruit with green abdomen. Credits: 17 & 18. Wynand Uys. 19. Peter Webb.

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